

Mathematical objections to the traditional interpretations of Special Relativity

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Abstract

This manuscript re-examines the conceptual and logical foundations of Special Relativity, starting with a reassessment of Herbert Dingle's symmetry objection. Through a rigorous analysis of the Minkowski metric and its derivation via orthogonal signal triangulation, we investigate whether the breakdown of simultaneity implies a concomitant collapse of invariant logical propositions ($P \wedge Q$) across inertial frames. We demonstrate that the traditional interpretations of time dilation and length contraction often rely on a choice of geometric representation rather than ontological necessity. By deriving the Minkowski metric from elementary Euclidean principles and invariant orthogonal coordinates, we expose a fundamental tension between the mathematical formalism of Special Relativity and the requirements of traditional logical coherence. The work concludes that without a preferred frame of reference to preserve the order of events, the theory's interpretation remains epistemologically ambiguous, challenging the perceived universality of its underlying geometric structure.

1 Introduction

The physicist Herbert Dingle, in his book *Science at the Crossroads*, presented the following objection to special relativity:

According to the special theory of relativity, two similar clocks, A and B, which are in uniform relative motion and in which no other differences exist of which the theory takes any account, work at different rates. The situation is therefore entirely symmetrical, from which it follows that if A works faster than B, B must work faster than A. Since this is impossible, the theory must be false.

Dingle's objection, despite its clarity, was never published in any scientific, mathematical, or philosophical journal. According to his own account, most re-

sponses from physicists were dismissive, and the rejection he received from peer review claimed that his critique was based on an “elementary mistake.”

But this situation should itself raise suspicion. If a theory implies a violation of elementary logic, then the objection must be clearly refuted in equally elementary terms, because logic is the foundation of all scientific discourse and, therefore, not something negotiable, nor a matter of convenience. When the interpretation of mathematical structures appears to undermine logical coherence, then the burden of clarification falls not just on the critic, but on the community that defends the theory.

Dingle’s example is instructive not because it proves relativity false, but because it shows how easily a theory can be defended with rhetorical distance instead of direct conceptual clarity. If we are to avoid repeating that history, we must be willing to interrogate even the “elementary mistakes”—for they may not be mistakes at all, but unasked questions.

In this manuscript, I return to Dingle’s concerns—but with a different angle. I will not argue from the relativity of motion, which I consider mathematically inconsistent for reasons I will later explain. My aim is very similar: to show that special relativity appears to be incompatible with traditional logic. However, the argument I present depends on a result derived solely from the Minkowski metric, as will also be shown later on. But just like Dingle’s objection, this argument is remarkably simple to state in casual terms.

Thus, according to special relativity, simultaneity depends on the choice of inertial frame. That is, what one observer A describes as two events happening “at the same time” (say, the logical proposition $P \wedge Q$), another observer B may not describe as simultaneous. This is not just a shift in coordinates—it challenges whether both observers can even agree on the logical truth of the same statement. That alone should raise philosophical concerns.

My main issue is that I find traditional interpretations of special relativity conceptually misleading and lacking transparency. Thus, I now take on the imperative task of revisiting every assumption and result that I consider necessary in order to establish a clearer conceptual framework—one that allows at the very least a precise interpretation of Dingle’s objection and of my own revised version.

Although I am not a physicist by training, I approach these questions from the perspective of mathematics—and, more importantly, with the philosophical conviction that logic is not up for negotiation if we are to preserve coherent scientific knowledge. If the formal tools used in physics give rise to interpretations that imply contradictions or undermine basic logical coherence, then those tools require a more careful conceptual treatment—especially when their application involves elementary mathematical notions.

2 Non-uniqueness of solution

The standard presentation of special relativity tends to treat Minkowski space as a natural or even inevitable structure, as if spacetime "came equipped" with a specific quadratic form that determines the physics. However, this view overlooks the fact that the invariance of the Minkowski interval — while suggestive — does not mathematically require the standard Lorentz transformations. When one demands that a quadratic form to be preserved under linear maps, there are infinitely many solutions, not just the one given by the Lorentz boost formula.

Suppose we have two vector spaces A and B with basis vectors $\{(\alpha_1, 0), (0, \alpha_2)\}$ and $\{(\beta_1, 0), (0, \beta_2)\}$ respectively and we would like to find a linear transformation $\mathcal{H} : A \rightarrow B$ such that for any vector $a = (a_1, a_2) \in A$ and the transformation $\mathcal{H}(a) = (b_1, b_2)$, the following quadratic equation holds:

$$c^2 a_2^2 - a_1^2 = c^2 b_2^2 - b_1^2$$

If we want to obtain the matrix

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} J & K \\ F & G \end{pmatrix}$$

that is related to this linear transformation \mathcal{H} , we can inspect what happens with the basis vectors in the last quadratic equation and get

$$\alpha_1^2 = c^2 F^2 \alpha_1^2 - J^2 \alpha_1^2 \implies 1 = c^2 F^2 - J^2 \quad (1)$$

$$c^2 \alpha_2^2 = c^2 G^2 \alpha_2^2 - K^2 \alpha_2^2 \implies c^2 = c^2 G^2 - K^2 \quad (2)$$

Given that $\alpha_1 \neq 0$ and $\alpha_2 \neq 0$ otherwise, the basis vector would be $(0, 0)$. We can also take some vector that is a linear combination of the basis vectors $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \in A$ and multiply it by the matrix H to reach the equation:

$$(c^2 G^2 - K^2) \alpha_2^2 - (J^2 - c^2 F^2) \alpha_1^2 + 2\alpha_1 \alpha_2 (c^2 FG - JK) = c^2 \alpha_2^2 - \alpha_1^2$$

Using (12) and (13) leads to the equation:

$$2\alpha_1 \alpha_2 (c^2 FG - JK) = 0$$

which must be true for any vector including the case where $\alpha_1 \neq 0$ and $\alpha_2 \neq 0$. So, this means that in order for that equation to always be equal to zero is when

$$c^2 FG - JK = 0 \quad (3)$$

Now we have three equations and four unknowns and we have already inspected the basis vectors and a vector that is a linear combination of the basis

vectors. Thus, given that this is all the information we know about such vector spaces, we cannot have a unique solution to this problem. However, this problem in special relativity requires the following equation

$$K = vG$$

But this is a physical restriction not a mathematical one, we can take any function $f(v)$ instead of just v and the transformation would also be linear if v is some parameter that does not depend on the basis vectors.

This analysis shows that the quadratic invariance condition alone does not uniquely determine the Lorentz transformation. Therefore, any claim that the structure of Minkowski space alone determines special relativity is mathematically unfounded. If space time is “equipped” with these Lorentz transformations is not only because space-time “calculates” quadratic forms but because it also must be “aware” of the “relative” speed v .

However, arriving at such equation is straight forward if we consider that the transformation matrix can be applied to coordinates and intervals of time and space that is, for two pairs of vectors

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} J & K \\ F & G \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} J & K \\ F & G \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} B_1 \\ B_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

We can subtract both equations to get

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_1 - a_1 \\ A_2 - a_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} J & K \\ F & G \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} B_1 - b_1 \\ B_2 - b_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

We can use this result to say that for some object at rest $x = x_1 - x_0 = 0$ after some unit time interval $1 = t_1 - t_0$, it transforms into the vector

$$\begin{pmatrix} J & K \\ F & G \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} K \\ G \end{pmatrix}$$

But an object at rest for the other observer must move with some speed v .

Thus, we finally have the equation we were looking for $K = vG$ and use this in equation (2), to get

$$c^2G^2 - K^2 = c^2G^2 - v^2G^2 \implies G^2 = \frac{c^2}{c^2 - v^2} = \frac{1}{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

We use once again the identity $K = vG$ in equation (3)

$$c^2FG - JK = c^2G(F - v/c^2J) = 0$$

If we assume that $c \neq 0$ then, $G \neq 0$ and obtain $F = v/c^2J$. Knowing this information, we can substitute into (1) to arrive at the last identity

$$J^2 - c^2F^2 = J^2 - v^2/c^2J^2 = 1 \implies J^2 = \frac{c^2}{c^2 - v^2} = \frac{1}{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

Taking into account all previous considerations, leads to the Lorentz matrix:

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} & \frac{v}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \\ \frac{v/c^2}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \end{pmatrix}$$

Which has an inverse given by

$$H^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} & -\frac{v}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \\ -\frac{v/c^2}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \end{pmatrix}$$

From now on, we will refer as the matrix with the minus sign as the negative Lorentz transformation and the other as the positive Lorentz transformation.

There is a more elegant way to write the previous matrix by substituting

$$\tanh \phi = v/c$$

We obtain the following matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} \cosh \phi & \sinh \phi \\ \frac{1}{c^2} \sinh \phi & \cosh \phi \end{pmatrix}$$

If $c = 1$ this is known as an **hyperbolic rotation** because for a fixed vector (b_1, b_2) , if we move the angle ϕ , the curve plotted is an hyperbola. This can be easily proven by just checking the quadratic difference:

$$a_1^2 - a_2^2 = (b_1 \cosh \phi + b_2 \sinh \phi)^2 - (b_1 \sinh \phi + b_2 \cosh \phi)^2 = b_1^2 - b_2^2$$

From the last calculation it's obvious that hyperbolas are "fixed" curves, that is, a hyperbola is transformed into the same hyperbola. However, there is another particular curve that is also fixed and it's the speed of light because if we take $x = ct$ then, Minkowski metric implies

$$0 = c^2t^2 - c^2t^2 = c^2t'^2 - x'^2 \implies |x'| = |ct'|$$

There is another geometric result that may come in handy for later discussions and is that Lorentz transformations transform straight lines into straight lines. This can be shown by taking a straight line $(\phi\alpha, \alpha)$, where ϕ is the slope of the straight line and transform this into

$$\beta_1 = \frac{\phi\alpha + v\alpha}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} = \frac{(\phi + v)\alpha}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

$$\beta_2 = \frac{\phi\alpha v/c^2 + \alpha}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} = \frac{(\phi v/c^2 + 1)\alpha}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

If we take the ratio β_1/β_2 , it yields

$$\beta_1 = \frac{\phi + v}{\phi v/c^2 + 1} \beta_2$$

Since v and ϕ are fixed and that the point $(0, 0)$ is also fixed, we can conclude that straight lines that contain the origin, transform into straight lines, although with a different slope. The same argument can be used if we instead take the negative Lorentz transformation for some line $(\theta\beta, \beta)$ and arrive at the formula

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{\theta - v}{1 - \theta v/c^2} \alpha_2$$

However, in general, it's not obvious if Lorentz transformations preserve curve shapes other than hyperbolas and straight lines. An strict proof of this statement is not necessary for any of the following discussions yet, a simple plot of a transformed parabola (α^2, α) is enough to convince us that we cannot assume that any curve preserves its "shape" under Lorentz transformations given that a linear transformation is not a reparametrization of the curve.

3 Length contraction and time dilation

Once this matrix is obtained, physicists obtain a result that is very conceptually misleading for this linear transformation. Physicists argue that for a rod, represented in this scenario as $(L, 0)$ in one frame it experiences length contraction and for a clock at rest experiences some time interval $(0, t)$ it will experience time dilation. We can notice how these physical properties of rods and clocks refer to the basis vectors. However, these results are somewhat confusing.

From now on, we will follow physics standard notation that usually writes the

Figure 1: Transformed parabola with Lorentz transformations.

Lorentz transformations as the equations:

$$x' = \frac{x - vt}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}},$$

$$t' = \frac{-xv/c^2 + t}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

This implies that for a vector $(x', t') \in B$ the positive Lorentz transformation is applied and results in a vector $(x, t) \in A$, that is, we also have the equations:

$$x = \frac{x' + vt'}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}},$$

$$t = \frac{x'v/c^2 + t'}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

Thus, if one thinks there is time dilation and length contraction, the expected relation between times should be $t' = M'$ where $M > 1$ and for distances $x' = mx$ where $m < 1$. But this is incorrect as we can realize by inspecting Einstein's interpretations:

The rigid rod is thus shorter when in motion than when at rest, and the more quickly it is moving the shorter the rod.

As a consequence of its motion the clock goes more slowly than when at rest.

Thus, we can think this interpretations mathematically as having a scaling factor $\lambda < 1$ for a vector in the frame in motion ($t' = \lambda t$, $x' = \lambda x$). However, even with this clearer picture, these statements are algebraically misleading given that are obtained by focusing only on the basis vectors of the vector space A . We can inspect what happens to the base vectors $\{(x', 0), (0, t')\} \subset B$ after applying the positive Lorentz transformation. Let's take the vector $(x, 0)$ first:

$$x'((x', 0)) = \frac{x'}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \quad t'((x', 0)) = \frac{x'v/c^2}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

But we can also take the basis vector $(0, t')$ to get

$$x'((0, t')) = \frac{vt'}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \quad t'((0, t')) = \frac{t'}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

This is not consistent with the time dilation and length contraction canonical interpretation since we can see now how both $x'((x, 0))$ and $t'((0, t))$ are scaled by the same factor $(1 - v^2/c^2)^{-1/2} > 1$. The derivation of the length contraction results comes from some *rebranding* of variables that can be obtained by taking the basis vector $(x, 0) \in A$ that results into:

$$x'((x, 0)) = \frac{x}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \quad t'((x, 0)) = \frac{-xv/c^2}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

And now the other basis vector $(0, t)$ for time dilation:

$$x'((0, t)) = \frac{-vt}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \quad t'((0, t)) = \frac{t}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

This tell us that both spaces A and B can experience “slowing down of clocks and contraction of rods” but, like I said, this is algebraically misleading and confusing. Previous results merely tell us, from a purely mathematical point of view, that the scaling factor is the same for **some basis vectors** after applying the transformation or its inverse. Although, it is worth mentioning that there are two vectors in particular where this does not happen, in such cases, the relation has a negative sign.

Thus, while physical experiments may confirm effects interpreted as time dilation or length contraction, it must be acknowledged that these effects are not intrinsic to the linear transformation itself. They rely on specific operational definitions and physical conventions. Algebraically, both space and time directions are not uniformly scaled by the same factor.

Moreover, since the Lorentz transformation ultimately arises as a solution to a quadratic constraint—the invariance of the Minkowski norm—it admits multiple branches and sign ambiguities. This further reinforces the need for caution when attributing physical meaning to specific algebraic components without carefully considering the global geometric or algebraic structure.

4 Relativity of motion

The standard interpretation of both reference frames experiencing clock slowing is usually presented as a corollary of relativity of motion. However, there’s no clear reason to privilege such interpretation over another, equally valid one: viewing the negative Lorentz matrix not as B seeing A move with velocity $-v$, but as a transformation from a rest frame A into a moving frame B . In this section, we examine this idea to challenge the assumption of the relativity of motion.

It is worth noting that Einstein himself, in his early writings, did not treat the “moving nature” of inertial frames as an a priori truth, but rather as an empirical assumption:

For the physical description of natural processes, neither of the reference bodies K , K' is unique (lit. "specially marked out") as compared with the other. Unlike the first [the principle of relativity¹], this latter statement need not of necessity hold a priori; it is not contained in the conceptions of "motion" and "reference-body" and derivable from them; only experience can decide as to its correctness or incorrectness.

Following this reasoning, the decision to label one frame as “in motion” and another as “at rest” is often justified by practical considerations rooted in our everyday intuition that labels rockets or embankments as frames in motion. But mathematically, using Lorentz transformations, one can make a case against the assumption that this choice is or should be arbitrary.

Let’s take a naive approach first since, as we stated before, we can consider the negative Lorentz transformation as the transformation from the frame at rest to the

¹Principle of relativity can be stated shortly as: If relative to K , K' is moving uniformly, then natural phenomena run their course with the same general laws.

one in motion. In this case relativity of motion would mean that we could choose freely between

$$a = Hb, \quad \text{or} \quad b = Ha$$

for $a \in A$ and $b \in B$. But this implies that

$$a = H^2a$$

Although, this identity does not hold for the Lorentz matrix... and, actually, not even for Galilean transformations. So, our naive approach seems to be telling us that there are some physical considerations in choosing either $a = Hb$ or $b = Ha$. Although, these considerations are very intuitive for the Galilean transformation since we have the two scenarios

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x' + vt & \text{or} & & x' &= x + vt \\ x' &= x - vt & \text{or} & & x &= x' - vt \end{aligned}$$

The difference is just a sign in the speed v which somehow is very intuitive that it is an arbitrary decision. But with Lorentz transformations, the ambiguity is not so benign. For instance, consider two events that are simultaneous in one frame—i.e., they satisfy $\Delta t = 0$ or $\Delta t' = 0$. The Lorentz transformations show that such events are no longer simultaneous in the other frame:

$$t((x', 0)) = \frac{x'v/c^2}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \quad t'((x, 0)) = \frac{-xv/c^2}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

So, depending on the chosen direction of transformation, one frame will assign a negative time difference to a pair of events that are simultaneous in the other. What does this negative time mean?

One might argue that past and future are also arbitrary conventions. But that's not the real issue. The real issue is: why is past and future arbitrary for simultaneous measures? Also, if we follow Einstein's interpretations, wouldn't a clock with negative time may be interpreted as a clock moving backwards? Whatever we may interpret that negative time, I think we should still follow Einstein's own remarks, we are not justified in treating both frames as physically indistinguishable purely from the structure of the transformations. We must appeal to experience. But our everyday experience does not indicate that clocks run backwards or whatever when switching reference frames.

However, even if we make an argument that settles the last discussion, we can still inspect the Lorentz transformations to verify that relativity of motion it's algebraically inconsistent.

Let us consider instead a light pulse such that $x = ct$, but we already from section 2 that this implies $x' = ct'$. Therefore, if we consider the case where $x \neq 0$, we have the following proportions between these quantities:

$$\frac{x}{t} = \frac{x'}{t'} = c \implies \frac{x}{x'} = \frac{t}{t'} = h$$

Since we can freely choose the transformation, we take:

$$x = \frac{x' + vt'}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \quad t = \frac{x'v/c^2 + t'}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

We can divide by x' in the first equation and by t' in the second and obtain

$$h = \frac{x}{x'} = \frac{t}{t'} = \frac{1 + v/c}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

However, when we consider relativity of motion we can also choose

$$x' = \frac{x + vt}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \quad t' = \frac{xv/c^2 + t}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

Which leads to the very same relation but with inverted quotients

$$h = \frac{x'}{x} = \frac{t'}{t} = \frac{1 + v/c}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

In particular we can take the length quotients to obtain

$$\frac{x'}{x} = \frac{x}{x'} \implies x^2 = x'^2$$

Therefore, this would mean that we are in the same coordinate or frame or just another one with a rotation of π degrees of one or both of its axis. Thus, if we allow to make arbitrary choices of the frame that takes the positive transformation, this leads to only allow the transformation to apply into the very same vector space or one that has change of sign in its axis. There's no mathematical argument out of this. More than that, this result is not exclusive to the Lorentz transformations, it applies to any linear transformation that leaves some straight line $x = mt$ fixed in both frames as we can see from considering in general

$$x = Jx' + Kt' \implies \frac{x}{x'} = J + K/m$$

But if we can apply our linear transformation freely then we also get

$$x' = Jx + Kt \implies \frac{x'}{x} = J + K/m$$

This analysis would suggest that we must abandon the interpretation of the negative Lorentz transformation as the transformation from the rest frame to the moving one. If we are to take the principle of relativity seriously—namely, that no inertial frame is preferred—then the transformation must preserve symmetry. However, we have shown that there is a fundamental asymmetry for simultaneous events: one frame yields a positive time coordinate while the other yields a negative one. This asymmetry contradicts the very spirit of the principle of relativity of motion.

In conclusion, every attempt to reconcile the Lorentz transformations with the idea of full symmetry between inertial frames—under the assumption of relativity of motion—leads either to trivial identities, algebraic inconsistencies, or asymmetries that contradict the very principle we sought to preserve. The proportional contradictions, the breakdown under simultaneous events, and the failure to maintain transformation consistency all suggest that the assumption of reciprocal frame equivalence becomes untenable when the speed of light is postulated to be absolute. This stands in contrast to Galilean relativity, where relative motion is both intuitive and algebraically harmless. But once we declare light's speed invariant across all frames, we may have unknowingly also anchored something long rejected: the existence of a preferred frame, an absolute rest.

From this assertion of absolute rest and absolute motion—the speed of light—, one would expect that no arguments like the Twins' paradox or the Dingle objection should question the value of the Lorentz transformations. But, as have stated at first, this paradoxical nature of special relativity may be grounded within the non-simultaneity nature, not in the relativity of motion. We can give an example to show this paradoxical nature but we may have to face a very questionable definition of modern physics: the proper interval.

5 Energy conservation

Modelation of the evolution of physical systems is heavily dependent on the idea of conservation laws, one of the most well known is the conservation of energy. This energy conservation is true through time intervals, no matter what time window we choose the energy of the system is the same if there are no external forces. Thus, this imposes a problem for special relativity because now observers perceive different times so, energy conservation is not straight forward. In order to solve

this matter, physicists came with a solution by defining a new parameter, the proper interval for some vector (x, y, z, t) as

$$d\tau^2 = c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2$$

From a mathematical point of view, this is completely arbitrary. There's no one that could stop me from using an arc-length parametrization from a time parameter curve $(x(t), y(t), z(t), t)$ like in differential geometry and use instead

$$\tau = (1/c) \int_{s_0}^s \sqrt{\left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dy}{dt}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dz}{dt}\right)^2} dt$$

With that $1/c$, we are also giving a parametrization that is invariant under the Minkowski metric since it will always move with the speed of light which is the same for all observers.

So, what's the reason for choosing one over the other? Because there's no way everything can move with the speed of light? That is not the idea behind the arc-length parametrization since it does not ignore the time measured by any of the observers, it's merely a convenient definition to have a parameter that works for both observers. But if we want to use a parameter for both observers why can't they choose t or t' ? After all, we have a linear transformation that allow us to use one or the other, right? Honestly, I have no idea what's the "official" answer from physicists to this matter but, as far as I am concerned, it's because that proper interval is the one you need to use Einstein's famous equation

$$E = \frac{mc^2}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

Although, we will show that this definition of energy is not necessary for energy conservation and even if we use that formula it does not require any *fancy* parametrizations.

Let's suppose we have observers A and B and A is seeing B moving with speed v_0 . Also, let's suppose we have with two time parameter curves $(x(t), t)$ in frame A and $(x'(t'), t')$ in frame B . Thus, for each observer they will measure its respective proper momentum:

$$p(t) = m \frac{dx}{dt}, \quad p'(t') = m \frac{dx'}{dt'}$$

Therefore, we would like to know if observer A , using his own coordinate time t , can compute a derivative of the position x' with his time t such that it reflects a

meaningful momentum in A 's frame. That is, can we define a function $p'(t)$ that can capture the change in motion but with his own time measurements.

$$p'(t) = m \frac{dx'}{dt} = mv$$

But we can calculate that derivative from the Lorentz transformations easily to get

$$\frac{dx'}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{x - v_0 t}{\sqrt{1 - v_0^2/c^2}} \right) = \frac{\frac{dx}{dt} - v_0}{\sqrt{1 - v_0^2/c^2}}$$

We would like to emphasize that we don't care about simultaneity. Conservation of energy doesn't require synchronized clocks across frames — it just requires that we can express physical quantities as functions of a common time parameter. Since t and t' are related by a linear and invertible transformation, we can express $x'(t')$ as $x'(t)$, and thus compute the derivatives with the chosen time parameter. For this case, this yields to the relativistic momentum

$$p'(t) = m \frac{\frac{dx}{dt} - v_0}{\sqrt{1 - v_0^2/c^2}} = \frac{p - mv_0}{\sqrt{1 - v_0^2/c^2}}$$

Also, we can calculate the relativistic momentum for the other observer that has basically the same structure

$$p(t') = m \frac{\frac{dx}{dt'} + v_0}{\sqrt{1 - v_0^2/c^2}} = \frac{p' + mv_0}{\sqrt{1 - v_0^2/c^2}}$$

We can clearly see how this behaves well for the $v_0 \ll c$ situation. However, we can still argue against our definitions of relativistic momentum since we should be comparing how the derivatives transform to compare the proper momentum $p(t)$ and $p'(t')$. Even in this scenario we still need to handle a time that works for both observers to apply the conservation of energy principle. Yet, I do not have any argument against this set up other than mathematical simplicity and that our previous formulation is consistent with the Galilean transformations. Our previous definitions of relativistic momentum are far more simple because the relationship between the derivatives is not obvious. A naive attempt to link derivatives across frames might involve applying the chain rule blindly:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{dx}{dx'} \frac{dx'}{dt'} \frac{dt'}{dt}$$

But such expressions break down unless we have an explicit inversion of $t'(x')$, which is not always available. Either way, if some solution is found for this issue, I don't see any reason to discard it as another valid definition of momentum that might lead to another definition of energy.

We can easily realize that if the proper momentum is conserved, therefore the relativistic momentum is conserved in both frames

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = \frac{dp'}{dt} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dp'}{dt'} = \frac{dp}{dt} = 0$$

Therefore we can define the energy for the frame A at rest as

$$E = \frac{1}{2}m \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$$

And the relativistic energy for the observer B as

$$E' = \frac{m(v - v_0)^2}{2\sqrt{1 - v_0^2/c^2}}$$

It's worth mentioning that this is the energy that is conserved with the time t from observer A . Yet, nothing can stop us from using the time t' from observer B to get

$$E' = \frac{1}{2}m \left(\frac{dx'}{dt'} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{2}mv'^2$$

With the respective relativistic energy

$$E = \frac{m(v' + v_0)^2}{2\sqrt{1 - v_0^2/c^2}}$$

So, what is going on? why do we have too many formulas for the energy? Basically because there is no universal formula of energy, even in the Galilean transformations, the relativistic energy

$$E' = \frac{1}{2}m(v - v_0)^2$$

It's not the same formula for the case where the observer is at rest $v_0 = 0$.

In this sense, energy conservation is not a property of a universal formula, but of the invariance under a particular choice of parameterization. Noether's theorem reminds us that conservation laws arise from symmetries—but it does not prescribe a unique form for the conserved quantity. Thus, the standard relativistic energy is

just one among many possible conserved expressions, contingent on the choice of time.

But we can take this discussion against the definition of the proper interval even further, since we can show that we also do not need such definition to obtain the Lagrangian that leads to Einstein's formula.

Let's consider first a particle moving in linear motion (vt, t) in frame A and for frame B the curve is $(v't', t')$. Therefore we have from the invariance of the Lorentz transformations that:

$$s^2 = c^2t^2 - v^2t^2 = c^2t'^2 - v'^2t'^2$$

Since s^2 it's invariant let's focus on the parameters from frame A and multiply by the squared mass m^2 of certain particle with constant mass m and divide by t^2 to obtain the **invariant momentum**:

$$p^2 = c^2m^2 - m^2v^2$$

We only need to multiply by c^2 to get to a formula that has energy squared units $\frac{g^2m^4}{s^4}$.

$$\varepsilon^2 = c^4m^2 - c^2m^2v^2 = m^2c^4(1 - v^2/c^2)$$

This quantity, which we may call the **invariant energy**, is constructed directly from the Minkowski metric and does not rely on any assumption of parametrization by proper time. However it does rely on mass conservation otherwise, it will not be a constant function on time. We can also notice how this invariance behaves since we have ignored the other side of the equation because it has a less intuitive interpretation but that ε can have two different expressions:

$$\varepsilon^2 = m^2c^4(1 - v^2/c^2) = m^2c^4 \frac{t'^2}{t^2} (1 - v'^2/c^2) = m^2c^4 \frac{(-vv_0/c^2 + 1)^2}{1 - v_0^2/c^2} (1 - v'^2/c^2)$$

Where v_0 is the speed at which A sees B is moving and the ratio t/t' is obtained from the Lorentz transformation formulas.

At this point, one might ask: What does ε actually represent? Is it the Lagrangian? The Hamiltonian? The kinetic energy? In truth, it is none of these specifically and all we can say is that it is an invariant scalar derived purely from the geometry of spacetime and mass conservation. Its interpretation depends on the context and choice of parameter, not on any universal definition. In order to make it clear that this invariant scalar is not necessarily the Lagrangian or the kinetic energy, we can replace the constant mass m by some constant charge q to obtain the formula

$$\varepsilon_q^2 = q^2c^4(1 - v^2/c^2)$$

But a charged particle must have a potential attached to its energy or Lagrangian. Therefore, the interpretation of this quantity becomes more ambiguous in the scope of Lagrangian mechanics, but as we have stated, this quantity is just some invariance that follows from the geometry of the space.

Reader may be wondering how can this be generalized for any curve not just straight lines. Well, we can prove that if one has a parameter θ such that it can parametrize smooth curves $(x(\theta), t(\theta))$ in frame A and $(x'(\theta), t'(\theta))$ in frame B , we also have the Minkowski invariance for derivatives

$$c^2 \left(\frac{dt}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dx}{d\theta} \right)^2 = c^2 \left(\frac{dt'}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dx'}{d\theta} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

This identity—whose proof follows directly from the Lorentz transformations but it's left at the Appendix—shows that no specific parametrization (neither t , nor t' , nor τ) is privileged. The Minkowski norm remains invariant regardless of the choice of θ , provided it is a valid parameterization of the curves.

Hence, by taking $\theta = t$, we recover the same expression for the invariant energy

$$\varepsilon^2 = c^4 m^2 - c^2 m^2 \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 = m^2 c^4 (1 - v^2/c^2)$$

Thus, this Minkowski invariant energy does not even need a parametrization by proper time. However it does rely on a specific choice of that time because we can also have the representation with time t' by

$$\varepsilon'^2 = c^4 m^2 - c^2 m^2 \left(\frac{dx'}{dt'} \right)^2 = m^2 c^4 (1 - v'^2/c^2)$$

It's worth mentioning that $\varepsilon \neq \varepsilon'$ because the invariance of the derivatives holds when the parameter of the curves is the same in both frames and it cannot be the same equation for different parameters $\theta = t$, $\theta = t'$ or $\theta = \tau$. So, whatever our choice is, this is not a problem for Noether's theorem since this theorem assures us that energy conservation follows from time translation invariance—but it says nothing about which time we must use. In this light, the definition of energy is not absolute, but contingent upon the chosen parameter under which dynamics are described.

We can say, in conclusion, that the Einstein's energy formula is a consequence of Minkowski invariance, not of any special status granted to the proper interval. Despite the heavy emphasis in standard literature (e.g., in Rindler's or Misner, Thorne & Wheeler's treatments) on the role of proper time in defining relativistic dynamics, such reliance is pedagogically convenient but not necessary from a mathematical or physical standpoint.

We would like to add an encore to our previous discussion, since now we can give another meaning to Einstein's famous equation

$$E = mc^2$$

because now we know how to obtain such formula from the invariant energy for a particle at rest $x = 0$. But from equation (4) that represents the invariance of the derivatives, we know that there is something else missing to that energy and is the time derivative dt/dt since we are taking the time of observer A as our parameter. Hence, the energy mc^2 can be thought as the energy that is related to the motion in time and we can notice how this concept is not required at all in Newtonian mechanics where everything moves in time at the same rate, but that is not the case for Lorentz transformations so, it makes sense to consider the "inertia" of time.

Going back to our main topic that concerns about using proper time or not, I hope this last discussion makes it clear that the standard discourse treats proper interval it as a kind of "universal parameter" or as the "real time of the particle" that transcends the choice of frame and resolves ambiguities related to time and energy. But it appears to be not only an unnecessary parameter but also a definition that hinders physical conceptualization of further definitions.

However, even if we would like to commit ourselves to the use of proper time, mathematics and physics seem to go separate ways because the most intuitive approach to the proper interval, from a purely mathematical standpoint, is by treating it as a some differential 1-form over a curve. Such curve obviously has no way to resolve ambiguities of choosing between the time of the observers because such differential form, when it needs to be integrated, it demands a parametrization of the curve either by t or t' , and the integral that results from either time is definitely not the same.

This can be better understood with an example for an object moving in linear motion for an observer A at rest $(\theta t, t)$ that will also move in linear motion for the moving observer B but at different speed $(\phi t', t')$. Therefore, we can evaluate the integral of the proper time in two different ways:

$$\begin{aligned}\tau &= \int \sqrt{c^2 dt^2 - dx^2} = \int \sqrt{c^2 - \theta^2} dt = \sqrt{c^2 - \theta^2} t \\ \tau' &= \int \sqrt{c^2 dt'^2 - dx'^2} = \int \sqrt{c^2 - \phi^2} dt' = \sqrt{c^2 - \phi^2} t'\end{aligned}$$

So, even if we know that the proper interval is Minkowski invariant, the integral is not the same when we need to choose a parametrization of the curve. This is even more evident for a particle at rest $(0, t)$ in A which gives the formulas

$$\tau = ct, \quad \tau' = \sqrt{c^2 - \phi^2} t'$$

These are two different straight lines with different slopes and it cannot be possible for that particle to be at rest in both frames so $\phi \neq 0$. Yet both expressions are derived from integrating the same Lorentz-invariant differential form. Not only that, even if we assume that $\tau = \tau'$, this implies that

$$\frac{t}{t'} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \phi^2/c^2}}$$

Which is not true for all x and t in our vector space. This shows that, despite its invariance in its differential expression, the integral of the proper interval is not invariant under reparametrization of the curve. More than that if we take the previous formulas proper interval is not a proper time since it's a length not a time interval in order to make the proper interval as a proper time is by taking

$$\tau = t, \quad \tau' = \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} t'$$

Nevertheless, whether we use the proper interval as length or time, this is the breaking point for physics and mathematics. Because in physics, you cannot use the proper interval as an integral over a differential form that changes with different curves. Physicists use the proper interval to describe the “real time” of the particle, that is, you must assume the particle is at rest which by definition will force you to use either of the previous two formulas. But this is just going around in circles since if we take $t = \tau$ we already have what's the relation with the time t' of the other frame from the Lorentz transformations themselves but now we are forcing a particle to be at rest $x' = 0$.

Even more, this restriction is just a particular case of our discussion that leads to the Einstein's formula for energy because we are not assuming a particle at rest in any of the frames. However, from our deduction of Einstein's formula, we explained that there are two cases when you consider t or t' as the parameter. And this dilemma is not solved by the proper interval, after all, due to the relativity of motion, every inertial observer can claim to be at rest. Which means we can also take the formulas

$$\tau' = t', \quad \tau = \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} t$$

So, this definition simply shifts the ambiguity rather than resolving it. Thus, the proper interval is just another name given to a formula we already had before that now is imposing the restriction for objects to always be at rest, which may lead to an overly complicated approach to certain problems, like having many particles, when one could just use the Lorentz transformations from “scratch” with any unnecessary restrictions.

As a side note, it's worth mentioning that if we consider our discussion that the Lorentz transformations are incompatible with relativity of motion then, the proper

interval is just a differential getting in our way since there's no way we can assume every particle to be at rest due to having an absolute rest.

In conclusion, there's no need to invoke any privileged parameter to work with relativistic dynamics either from a conceptual or mathematical stand point and from now on, we will no longer consider this definition, as it restricts our reasoning to an artificial and unnecessary conceptual constraint.

6 A magical apple tree

Once upon a time, in a prosperous and wondrous kingdom, there lived two non-identical twins: Alice and Bob. One day, Bob had to embark on a space journey. But since both siblings were deeply devoted to the Magic Goddesses, they were blessed with magical apple trees—trees that bore one apple per month, even aboard a cold and lonely spaceship.

These mystical trees produced apples of different colors and flavors. Alice kept a pink-apple tree on Earth, and Bob brought a blue-apple tree aboard his spacecraft.

We now ask: after a month has passed, how many pink apples does Alice have? And how many blue apples does Bob have?

Because of their devotion, the Magic Goddesses also blessed Bob with a spaceship capable of instantly accelerating to a speed $v = c\sqrt{3}/2$. In this case we know that

$$\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} = \frac{1}{2}$$

Let us first make calculations in Alice frame after a month on Earth given that $v = c\sqrt{3}/2$ and that a tree is at rest at some point on the Earth and the spaceship, that is $x = 0$ and $r = 0$, we get:

$$t(r = 0) = \frac{rv/c^2 + u}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} = 2u$$

But as we have seen the result is symmetrical for objects at rest so, for Bob's frame at the spaceship we have

$$u(x = 0) = \frac{-xv/c^2 + t}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} = 2t$$

Thus, we can see that when it's been two months for Alice at Earth $t = 2$ it has only passed one on the spaceship $u = 1$, therefore, Alice has two pink apples and Bob has only one blue apple. But we also arrive at the exact same equation for Bob's frame. So, when two months have passed on the spaceship $u = 2$, only one has passed on Earth $t = 1$, thus, when Bob has two apples Alice only has one.

This relationship between the amount of apples it's not inverse in spite of using the inverse Lorentz transformations, both are claiming that their other sibling always has the double of apples. After realization of this issue, Alice and Bob had no other way to solve this than stop praying to the Magic Goddesses for giving them contradictory apple trees and they lived happily ever after.

Well, that's the story as mama told me. But Mama didn't count on me actually confronting the Magic Goddesses about it and they, with their beautiful and charming voice, told me that they provide no faulty apple trees. Alice and Bob de-conversion is grounded on their poor understanding of that linear transformation that does not guarantee conservation of apples given by magical trees. These transformations ought to preserve the laws of physics, as the principle of relativity states, and magical apple trees are not part of this principle. But not only that, Magic Goddesses also told me that this is not the only misconception because Lorentz transformations depend on time and space. For instance Bob's calculations are $t(r = 0, u)$ but in Alice's frame $r = 0$ is a moving object with speed $x = vt$. So, she must make the calculations:

$$u(x = c\sqrt{3}, t = 2) = 2((-c\sqrt{3})(c\sqrt{3}/2)/c^2 + 2) = -3 + 4 = 1$$

Which means that if there was a magical pink apple tree in Bob's spaceship synchronized with Alice's apple tree, then it will always have twice the blue apples Bob has. And the inverse relationship also holds, if there was a blue apple tree on Earth, it will produce twice the pink apples Alice has. However, this apple trees in spite of being magical cannot be in two places at once. So, that calculations are for some hypothetical apple tree existing simultaneously in two places at once. Thus, their discussion of who has more apple trees is founded not in observations but in calculations of some hypothetical object.

The real lesson that the Magic Goddesses told me I should learn from this is that, this issue of who has more apples is not a problem of the interpretation of the transformations, the real issue comes from not understanding why Alice and Bob time perception can be different and there's no way you can infer that from the Lorentz transformations or the Minkowski metric, because such premises already assume that times are different between observers. There's no way you can objectively tell who has more apples given that there's no universal time to make such calculations. Thus, the only way Alice and Bob can pray again to the magic Goddesses may occur when they actually figure out why observers perceive different times by a discussion that does not involve the very same transformations that already assume such situation holds.

And that's the moral of the story: you cannot explain the relativity of time using the very transformations that presuppose it.

I sincerely hope this parody of a fairy tale helps the reader understand my obsession to discredit the proper interval since even from our discussion that rejects the idea of the relativity of motion, this problem of the contradictory apple trees still holds because it's a consequence derived from the Lorentz transformations. So, it seems very suspicious when physicists try to solve a problem like the twins' paradox through proper interval when it does not solve any ambiguity since, due to relativity of motion, you can also consider the other observer at rest just like Dingle stated more than half a century ago

To make things even worse, proper interval does not solve the problem of the ambiguity of measurements, it is usually solved by considering the "true" frame as the non-accelerated frame, which leads to a calculation that can be done with only the Lorentz transformations and not by introducing the very same parameter but with a *fancy* name. Because whether we side with the idea of an absolute rest like Lorentz or Poincare or with the non-preferred frame like Einstein, this contradiction of both observers stating that the other has twice the amount of apples still holds because is a property of the transformations that state that times between observers are different.

But this problem requires a very serious and proper philosophical treatment that has been unaddressed for more than a hundred goddamn years! But physicists, just like Alice and Bob, they live happily ever after —not because the contradiction was resolved, but because they chose not to look directly at it. To make things even worse, I'm not even the first to point this out. More than fifty years ago, Herbert Dingle tried to yell at physicists that something was wrong —but he received scarce response. Because in modern physics, if the math works, the paradox doesn't matter.

7 Frank-Einstein; or, The Metaphysical Prometheus

In 1818, Mary Shelley wrote what could be considered the first science fiction novel of all time: the story of a scientist haunted by his own horrendous creation. The title itself suggests a mythological reading—like Prometheus, Frankenstein is punished not by the gods but by the very being he obsessively brought to life.

More than two centuries later, we have become increasingly aware of how science and technology can turn against us in metaphorical ways not so different from Shelley's warning. Yet science is not just technology. Whether modern physicists like Stephen Hawking appreciate it or not, science is also philosophy.

In 1916, Albert Einstein published *Relativity: The Special and General Theory*, in which he questioned the notions of space and time that had been treated as *a priori* truths since Kant. In my view, special relativity is an even more un-

settling tale than Frankenstein—but from a metaphysical standpoint. Everyone is bewitched by its predictive power, yet few recognize the philosophical monster it harbors in plain sight.

The non-reciprocal nature of time measurements arises directly from the Minkowski metric when we consider an object at rest, $x' = 0$, moving at velocity v in another frame. This yields the familiar time dilation formula:

$$c^2 t'^2 = c^2 t^2 - v^2 t^2 = (c^2 - v^2) t^2$$

But if we assume relativity of motion then, an object at rest in the other frame $x = 0$ is going to move with speed $-v$. So, that leads to the very same formula but the times are swapped:

$$c^2 t^2 = c^2 t'^2 - v^2 t'^2 = (c^2 - v^2) t'^2$$

I abused notation a little, but those time measurements for objects at rest in different frames cannot be the same, otherwise we would have $t^2 = t'^2$.

If we try to reduce the Twins Paradox to mere relative rest states there's no principled way to say who aged more. We can no longer appeal to the "true" frame being the non-accelerated one to find out the "true" time measurement.

What I find most disturbing is that physicists rarely entertain the possibility that the model might be incomplete or metaphysically incoherent. Rather than confront this openly, they either retreat into mathematical formalism or resort to rhetorical evasion like Herbert Dingle experienced by rejecting his argument for being an "elementary mistake".

This type of discussion is not coincidence, I believe very deep down physicists are aware of the philosophical monster they must deal with if they ever consider the slight possibility that there's no way to objectively tell which one is the older brother. Yet, I'm no physicist so I'm not that afraid in facing such monster but also, after my visit to The Magic Heavens, the Magic Goddesses taught me a few spells to soothe down any kind of monster physical or metaphysical.

7.1 Sartre vs Aristotle: A Rod's Existential Crisis

Let's imagine we have a bunch of flies that want to name their Lord by doing a simple contest: the fly that can cross a rod of length L in shorter time will be the Lord of the Fly Kingdom. Although these flies are very good friends with Bob and they know he is such a nerd that is into science, math, books and boring stuff but they trust him to measure time lapses and makes sure there's no foul play like shrinking the rod or anything that could be considered cheating.

Besides, Alice and Bob are also good friends and he asks her to verify his measurements in her own frame, obviously Alice must compare Bob's transformed

measures with her observations, that is, if Bob says he measured distance x' and time t' , she must calculate the Lorentz transformation vector and verify it matches her data. Although, Alice is being tutored by Bob and he wants to test if her student can tell verify which one was the winner if he only sends the speed θ_i of each fly.

This problem can be solved, but it's better left as an exercise to the reader since it only requires an application of the Fizeau formula

$$\phi_i(\theta_i) = \frac{\theta_i + v}{\theta_i v / c^2 + 1}$$

Where ϕ_i and θ_i are the speeds for the i -th fly in frame A and B respectively. It may seem not obvious at first but this an increasing function so if there is some M which $\theta_i < \theta_M$ for all i , then $\phi(\theta_i) < \phi(\theta_M)$. Therefore, the fastest fly wins in both frames.

But now we are more interested in the philosophical discussion and I would like the reader to answer: What's the "true" speed of each fly?... Obviously no such thing exists because speeds are relative. Albeit, in spite of this relative measurement, we were able to find some formula that allows us to solve the problem of the winner of the race for both observers.

However, when it comes to the standard solution of the older brother in the Twins' Paradox, my eyes have not seen anyone yet trying to find a formula where ambiguities are put aside. Physicists have treated the Lorentz transformations as something that makes rods shrink and clocks run slower at high speeds, but none of this makes any sense if one tries to find the "true" length of rods or the "true" aging of a person.

This is where Aristotle starts to cry and Sartre lights up a cigarette.

Aristotle believed that things have essences. A rod has a length and a clock cannot go slower because none of its four causes—material, formal, efficient and final— are dependent on some relative speed measured by some observer. In an Aristotelian philosophy, those properties are part of what the thing is and it cannot change depending on who observes them. But in special relativity lengths and time intervals cannot be pinned down without referencing an external frame. No identity. No essence. Just performance.

Sartre would be proud. In his view, existence precedes essence—not just for humans but, as it seems, for relativistic flies too. The fly is not defined by its speed, its length or even its age; it is whatever those measurements become in relation to an observer. This would be the end of Aristotelian metaphysics... but plot twist: it's not.

Yet, in my opinion, this is one of the most bizarre plot twists I could imagine because physicists don't want to give up on Aristotle. Accepting Sartre's existentialism makes the Law of excluded middle about as useful as a lantern at noon.

But, I find physicists arguments to find out the "true" age of two brothers at different speeds as completely inaccurate. I don't know why they have just forgot that Lorentz transformations are not just transformations of relative times, lengths and speeds, but it's also a transformation with a fixed straight line that defines an absolute speed: the speed of light.

For a light beam there is no way we can reach non-reciprocal relations between observers. For a light pulse the formula that relates time between observers is

$$t = \frac{1 + v/c}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} t'$$

If we take the inverse Lorentz transformation we get

$$t' = \frac{1 - v/c}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} t$$

But the good news is that if we multiply the scaling factors the result is equal to one. Therefore, there is only one equation: $t = ht'$. We do not need to deal with two equations like the case for objects at rest in one frame or in the other. In conclusion, when we have measurements that involve objects at some speed that is not the speed of light we cannot rely on those measurements to be the "true" lengths or time intervals because speeds are relative, except one: the speed of light.

This should be checkmate for Sartre but physicists have no clue of if they are actually on Aristotle's side or not because the relativistic effects of time dilation and length contraction have been measured. Albeit, I have no idea what exactly they are measuring—but I cannot call it "true" time, given that some other observer moving at a different speed would disagree

So, now, the natural question is: How can I make a measurement that is not a "true" measurement? Well, that should not be a problem at all, even in classical mechanics there are no true measurements of kinetic energies since speeds are relative and even in that scenario conservation of energy remains true. Thus, in spite of relative measures, we can still work with the laws of physics that should be preserved by the relativity principle.

However, it's not hard to suspect that something odd is going on here because nobody cared about relative energies before but now physicists try to solve a problem of "true" or "real" age for some thought experiment when it is very obvious the formulas that are being used already assume relativity of measurements. This is where the real paradox resides: physicists accept that all measurements are relative, but suddenly demand an absolute resolution to a thought experiment that was constructed under the very premise that absolutes do not exist, which now this begs the question: why are physicists doing this?

I believe there are two obvious reasons why Twin’s paradox problem is such a mess. First reason is that working with different time measurements is more counter-intuitive than what it seems at first glance, and the second is that the Minkowski metric is hiding something more complicated than constant speed of light. The real deal is showing these matters through a somewhat convincing argument.

7.2 Mr. Tompkins in Magic Heavens

After Alice and Bob de-converted from their faith in the Magic Goddesses, they met Mr. Tompkins, an avid adventurer and occasional philosopher. Mr. Tompkins told them about a recent trip to the Magic Heavens, where he had a *simultaneous* vacation with his cousin in the ”real” Anime-Japan located within those same celestial realms.

However, he clarified that this was not a ”true” simultaneous trip—because although he and his cousin visited the same cities, they did so at different times.

”How can that be possible?” asked Alice and Bob, simultaneously.

Mr. Tompkins explained that their journey followed a very simple rule. Suppose we take the cities they visited as space coordinates:

$$\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}' = \{\text{Okinawa, Fukuoka, Hiroshima, Osaka, Kyoto, Tokyo, Sapporo}\}$$

And let the months of the year serve as time coordinates:

$$\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{T}' = \{\text{January, February, ... December}\}$$

Then the ”simultaneous”, yet non-simultaneous, trip followed the formula

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x' \\ t &= t' - vx \end{aligned}$$

Where v is just how fast you want to move through the months or seasons so you can watch the cherry trees at some cities. So, how does this work? Basically it means that Mr Tompkins is always at the same city that his cousin is but that at different time of the year. Therefore they are not always in Okinawa, they spend a month in each city even though, the month is not the same. Of course, this is perfectly possible in the Magic Heavens but certainly not in the real world because there’s no way two people can be at the very same place but at different times, right? Actually... if you had a time machine, perfectly possible, otherwise it’s not. However, for such a time machine to work within this model, we may need a brief philosophical discussion about two well-known theories of time: the A-theory and the B-theory.

The B-theory of time says that all moments—past, present, and future—are equally real. According to this view, change doesn't require anything to "come into being" or "pass away." Instead, change is just a difference between one point and another along the timeline. For example, a leaf is green on October 1st and red on October 15th. Both facts are equally real—just located at different points in time.

In this view, time is more like space: you don't "move through it" in any privileged sense—you just exist at your temporal location, and all other moments exist too, just like other places on a map. So if Mr. Tompkins is in Tokyo in April and his cousin is in Tokyo in November, they're simply at different time-locations of the same spatial point. Nothing paradoxical about it.

It seems, then, that the B-theory of time has the upper hand when it comes to moving along time coordinates. However, the A-theory of time states that at least some important forms of change require classifying events as past, present, or future. To accurately describe this kind of change, we need tensed propositions—there is a way the world is now, which was different in the past and will be different in the future.

If we refer back to our model, things get complicated when we try to combine this with the idea that both travelers move through time at different speeds. That idea seems to suggest that time is something one can "flow through" at different rates—an idea closer to the A-theory, where only the present is real, and "now" could even be replaced by "location" rather than "month."

For instance, if we had the traditional Galilean relativity equations, both observers could determine each other's position by sending a signal through all the cities. If the signal returns in the same month, it means they are at different cities but at the same time. In contrast, with the inverse-Galilean equations, the observer in the past could send a signal every month to the observer in the future. When it bounces back, he'll know the other was in Osaka in March—even if he himself is still in Hiroshima.

That doesn't violate any rules, since the past observer is in Hiroshima in March, and the future observer was in Osaka—but also in March. Therefore, can we make present-tense claims like: "Both are at Osaka on March and April"? Or should we say instead: "One was on March, and the other is on April tenselessly"?

So which is it? Do all moments coexist tenselessly, or is there a present replaced by the place? We can also say that after the end of the trip, Mr. Tompkins' cousin reached Sapporo in the year 2300 while he only got to 2025. So we're already comparing their "locations" as if there's a single, shared present—just experienced differently. But this introduces a subtle contradiction: a model that tries to work under B-theory assumptions, yet smuggles in a kind of A-theory dynamics.

The most practical resolution to this conundrum might be to prefer propositions

like: both observers are at Osaka and Hiroshima in July, regardless of which one considers that to be their “now.” This would favor the B-theory, where all events exist equally and independently of any presentness. But this resolution is grounded more in human linguistic convenience than in a true understanding of how motion through time should behave.

Thus, this brings us back to my earlier claim: working with different times for different observers is anything but intuitive. Why is it that no one raises philosophical objections when we use the classic Galilean setting with $t = t'$, yet as soon as we reverse it into $x = x'$, suddenly we’re in a conceptual minefield? A statement like “both observers are at the same city but at different times” already triggers doubt. Is that even a properly stated proposition, if one is in the future and the other in the past? Language, in this case, betrays us—since we typically reserve the word present for what is shared, not split.

On the other hand, these time-Galilean transformations—though they neither predict muon decay nor correct GPS systems—are conceptually far simpler than Lorentz transformations. And yet, it is surprisingly hard to find a satisfying way to describe even a basic scenario like two observers at the same place but at different times. What starts as a seemingly innocent case quickly spirals into linguistic, conceptual, and philosophical trouble. Even if we assume these observers have time machines, we’re still left asking: why—or even how—can one move through time in the first place?

In this “simultaneous” yet non-simultaneous journey of Mr. Tompkins and his cousin, we assume the situation is possible because it happens in the “magic realm.” But Lorentz transformations allegedly operate in this realm, the real one—not a fantastical one. So now we need to understand: why is time travel even possible? Some might argue that it’s because the Minkowski metric allows it. But that’s a circular argument: the metric already assumes that time is not absolute across observers. Others might say the constant speed of light implies this structure—but that’s precisely where things begin to blur. A constant speed of light does not imply a Minkowski metric.

8 The Emperor’s new Physics: constant speed of light

The modern era of physics began with an absence—not of phenomena, but of expected deviation. By the late 19th century, it was widely believed that light propagated through a subtle, invisible medium: the luminiferous ether. Like any medium, it was thought to provide a preferred frame of reference, and thus allowing the measurement of motion relative to it. To test this, Michelson and Morley designed an experiment to detect changes in the speed of light depending on the

Earth's motion through the ether. The result was baffling: no difference was observed. Light's speed appeared constant, regardless of direction.

Rather than abandon the ether, physicists like Lorentz and FitzGerald proposed increasingly elaborate hypotheses: that physical bodies contract when moving through the ether, and that time itself dilates. These assumptions, though unobservable directly, could preserve the form of Maxwell's equations—and they worked, mathematically. The Lorentz transformations were born, but they came at the cost of physical intuition.

Then came Einstein. In 1905, he discarded the ether entirely and postulated something radical in its place: the speed of light in vacuum is the same for all inertial observers. From this postulate, along with the principle of relativity, he derived the Lorentz transformations anew. Space and time were no longer absolute, and simultaneity became a relative concept.

Physics became relativistic.

But such a postulate, which seems modest at first glance—merely elevating an experimental observation to a foundational principle—carries hidden complexity. What begins as an empirical constraint quickly becomes a geometric imposition: it reshapes the way we define motion, compare reference frames, and ultimately conceive the structure of spacetime. But what I like to focus in this section at first is that constant speed of light is a very vague statement that by itself does not imply any particular transformation between observers unless further assumptions are considered.

8.1 Galilean constant speed of light

Let's assume we have an onserver A with a coordinate frame (x, t) and sees another observer B moving at speed v and lets also assume A sees some light pulste at some distance $x = ct$. Therefore, if speed of light is constant the distance at which observer B is from that light pulse is given by the equation $x' = ct'$ but we also know that observer B must be at some distance $x_1 = vt$ in A 's frame. Thus, we can calculate such distance x' as the difference

$$x' = x - x_1 = ct - vt = (c - v)t$$

This can be replaced in B 's observation for a light pulse to obtain

$$x' = (c - v)t = ct' \implies t' = (1 - v/c)t$$

Therefore this gives the transformation equations between observers as

$$\begin{aligned}x' &= x - vt \\t' &= (1 - v/c)t\end{aligned}$$

So, what's going on what are we doing "wrong"? Well, if we just assume constant speed of light. Nothing is wrong. However, I invite the reader to *troll* any physicist with such model in order to trigger his fundamentalism. The answer why the model is "wrong" is far more simple, yet not necessarily obvious, than many of the typical responses one would expect from a fundamentalist mindset.

These are what I consider may be the most typical objections to this model

- It violates the principle of relativity.
- Transformations must form a group.
- Your time transformation isn't symmetric under velocity inversion.
- Speed of light is not symmetric.
- It doesn't preserve the form of Maxwell's equations.
- Experiments confirm special relativity.

The last one, even though it's the most fundamentalist objection, is also the most interesting... at least at first, because the non-symmetric speed of light objection is the one that breaks the Pandora's box. Either way, empirical observations are important in the history of special relativity, we know that Einstein entered the scene when the Lorentz transformations were already accepted; the real challenge was explaining why objects contract or time dilates at high velocities. So, while our model may appear naive, it perfectly satisfies the requirement of the constant speed of light. It's not obvious why it should be discarded — unless one appeals to empirical observation.

We can actually categorize those objections into empirical and theoretical, that is, those grounded in mathematical or physical postulates. So, let us first inspect the first and second objections since it may appear that a mathematical structure may be derived from a physics principle because we may consider that the group structure of transformations between inertial frames is a consequence of the principle of relativity — namely, that objects should preserve their "natural" motion. However, in this model it is not obvious what the inverse transformation should be.

We could solve for x and t to get:

$$\begin{aligned}x &= x' + vt'/(1 - v/c) \\t &= t'/(1 - v/c)\end{aligned}$$

Or we might just change the sign of the velocity to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}x &= x' + vt' \\t &= (1 + v/c)t'\end{aligned}$$

It seems the latter is correct, since if observer B sees the light beam at a distance $x' = ct'$, observer A must add the distance from his origin to B 's origin, vt , to account for the total distance $x = (c + v)t$.

However, multiplying these two matrices does not yield the identity —meaning that we don't have a group structure.

However, this does not seem to violate the principle of relativity, if we put aside Maxwell equations, given that these transformations still preserve a Galilean structure. Any time parametric curve $(a(s), s)$ in one frame transforms into the same curve but parametrized by some factor $(1 \pm v/c)s$, along some straight line $\pm vs$, just like the typical Galilean transformations. Therefore, it may appear that group structure may guarantee the principle of relativity but it's a sufficient condition not a necessary one.

In conclusion, the only strong objection that compels us to discard this model is empirical: Maxwell's equations (themselves grounded in experiment) and the observed success of Lorentz transformations. From the standpoint of assuming only the constancy of the speed of light, we have no internal contradiction.

There is, however, another empirical observation that might more elegantly bury this model — but before addressing it, I would like to use this Galilean model to expose what I consider the most disturbing conceptual issue in Lorentz transformations.

In our Galilean model, simultaneity is preserved: what happens simultaneously in one frame happens simultaneously in the other. Let's suppose one observer is "moving faster in time" — say, after 30 days one reaches February while the other is already in March. Still, when both observers measure the height of a building, they agree it's 10 meters. If there's a TV show on Monday at 5 p.m., both observers see the same show when they reach that day and time.

Despite having different time rates, both observers conclude they're observing the same object. But in Lorentz transformations, where space and time coordinates always differ, how can we be so sure we're looking at the same object?

One possible answer is that it's the same object, just labeled differently. But our Galilean model makes this identity explicit — it's the same light beam at different distances from two points along a line and the resulting transformations agree with this consideration. Can we say the same for Lorentz transformations? Are we truly observing the same object — or even the same light pulse — when our measurements always differ in both time and space? There's no clear answer to this if we only assume the Minkowski metric. This ought to give our Galilean model the upperhand if we were to restrict ourselves only to *a priori* knowledge. Although, once we start to inspect the objection that the speed of light is not symmetric, this simple model starts to crumble too.

Let's take a light pulse such that $x = -ct$ then, the other observer must agree

with that speed. However, we can clearly see that taking the ratio of distance and time does not lead to that result

$$\frac{x'}{t'} = \frac{-(c+v)t}{(1-v/c)t} = \frac{-c(c+v)}{c-v} \neq -c$$

Here's where things get interesting. Our model depends on which light beam you're using for comparison. So, the transformation must be modified when dealing with a light pulse going in the opposite direction. That gives us a piecewise definition for the time coordinate:

$$t = \begin{cases} (1-v/c)t' & \text{if } c > 0 \\ (1+v/c)t' & \text{if } c < 0 \end{cases}$$

Again, you could argue against this formula for not being differentiable or even complain for not being a *plug-n'-play* formula. But that does not seem to be the real issue here, the main problem is actually trying to give a physical interpretation of that situation.

Einstein's interpretation of the Lorentz transformations was that clocks slow down when moving. But in this case, there's no obvious way to say what's going on physically when an observer's time depends on whether a light pulse goes to the right or to the left.

And here's the hot take: Lorentz transformations actually have the same kind of problem, just better disguised. We've already seen this with the Twins Paradox or with our earlier example of the magical apple trees. But if that's still not enough to convince the reader, there's yet another so-called "paradox" that reveals how, even more than a century later, no one really knows how to make physical sense of all this: the Andromeda paradox.

Roger Penrose in his book *The Emperor's New Mind: Concerning Computers, Minds, and the Laws of Physics* makes a discussion about what an observer may consider valid under his frame using the Lorentz transformations. Albeit, the author does not make any calculations, given that is a book intended for the general public. So, Penrose proposes the following discussion:

Two people pass each other on the street; and according to one of the two people, an Andromedan space fleet has already set off on its journey, while to the other, the decision as to whether or not the journey will actually take place has not yet been made. How can there still be some uncertainty as to the outcome of that decision? If to either person the decision has already been made, then surely there cannot be any uncertainty. The launching of the space fleet is an inevitability.

In fact neither of the people can yet know of the launching of the space fleet. They can know only later, when telescopic observations from Earth reveal that the fleet is indeed on its way. Then they can hark back to that chance encounter, and come to the conclusion that at that time, according to one of them, the decision lay in the uncertain future, while to the other, it lay in the certain past. Was there then any uncertainty about that future? Or was the future of both people already 'fixed'?

This discussion may rely in a previous paper by Hilary Putnam, where this author states that special relativity favors the tenseless notion of existence and, in order to reach such conclusion, Putnam appeals to the simultaneity of observers. What I find odd about this situation is how Penrose may appear to side with Putnam but not quite, since he also states that observers can only know for sure the information about the Andromeda galaxy after a light beam arrives at Earth, which make us question if Penrose and Putnam actually agree in what existence or knowledge means.

It's not the purpose of this manuscript to take a deep dive into this metaphysical waters, but what I find interesting is that the Putnam-Penrose interpretation is not in accordance to Einstein's interpretation of slowing down of clocks.

Yet, we may need to give Einstein some help to fit his ideas into our discussion because we also know that Einstein talked about clock's de-synchronization. Although, these two ideas, slowing down of clocks and clock de-synchronization, are not equivalent or a consequence of each other if one assumes the other, as we will see later on. But for now, let us just stick with Einstein's more general idea of clocks measuring different times because he was not talking about tenseless propositions or anything like that actually, if we take that Andromeda example, we may need to think of an experiment of why an observer may be able to synchronize his clock with one at Andromeda but the other observer at motion cannot.

Whatever our resolution is through this Einstein's framework, we can clearly see that, it also depends on a simultaneity argument just like Putman's discussion. Although, in this section we have seen that our Galilean model is in accordance with the constant speed of light, not without some mathematical complications like having a piecewise function, but this model still preserves simultaneity.

So, here comes the most unsettling question so far: if the breakdown of simultaneity for observers does not have a clear physical interpretation, shouldn't we also discard the Lorentz transformations like we did with the Galilean constant speed of light model for not having a clear interpretation of different time measurements?

Spoiler alert: We will not. Because we are going to explain non-simultaneity only with light beams, not by using tenseless propositions.

8.2 My final objection

I started this manuscript in the very same way that many physics textbooks do: just assuming the Minkowski metric. After that, we had to go through such an odyssey of mathematical considerations in order to propose an example similar to the Twin's paradox that does not involve acceleration, only to realize that, even if we take away the relativity of motion between observers, they cannot agree in their measurements.

Yet, it remains a mystery why, in the 120 years since Einstein published his article *On the Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies*, no resolution to this issue has been given in terms of the only equation that is not relative: the speed of light. This suggests there is something deeply wrong in the way these equations are being interpreted. Physicists are excellent at smashing particles in accelerators, but when it comes to resolving the most basic conceptual scenario—say, comparing the aging of brothers or counting apples from a magical apple tree—they seem to forget that the speed of light remains our only non-relative quantity.

My suspicions are almost too simple: that motion in time can be too counter-intuitive for our human experience, and that the Minkowski metric hides something far more complex than just a convenient encoding of constant speed of light. We are now close to untangling this *mysterious* encoding of the Minkowski metric, especially since our previous concerns—that we cannot even tell if we're looking at the same object in Lorentz transformations and that simultaneity does not arise from constant speed of light—demands a justification for the metric itself that can make a case against this ontological issue.

So, let us now attempt to derive the Minkowski metric from another empirical input we have so far overlooked: that time and space coordinates remain unaffected in the direction orthogonal to motion. This implies that objects must be moving in a space with more than one dimension. If we accept that then, the natural assumption is that objects move in three spatial dimensions.

Ironically, this very principle—unchanged orthogonal components—can be used both to derive the Minkowski metric and to discard it, at least for a general scenario with particles in three dimensions.

Thus, if we have an observer at rest A , another observer B moving on a straight line with constant speed v relative to A , and a light pulse traveling in a direction orthogonal to the line of motion of B , we obtain the situation shown in Figure 2.

Since this light pulse is orthogonal to A , its projection over the frame at rest A is zero. Thus, it's an object at rest for A which means the projection of the light pulse over the motion line of B is seen like an object that moves with some speed $\pm v$ and the motion of this projected light beam can be described by the equation $(x' = \pm vt', y' = 0, z' = 0, t')$.

Figure 2: Orthogonal ray for A and slanted ray for B

We also know that orthogonal directions are not affected by Lorentz transformations. Therefore, as we can see from Figure 2, we can apply the Pythagorean theorem to relate the lengths in A's frame and in the projection seen by B:

$$L^2 = y^2 + x^2 = c^2t'^2 + v^2t'^2$$

But L is the same light pulse although not orthogonal to B . So, from the constant speed of light postulate we have that $L = ct'$. So, this results into the equation

$$c^2t'^2 - v^2t'^2 = c^2t^2 \iff \frac{t'^2}{t^2} = \frac{c^2}{c^2 - v^2} \quad (5)$$

But we know that the constant speed of light makes the proportion of times and distances to be same. Therefore, for the distances L and y we have

$$\frac{L^2}{y^2} = \frac{c^2}{c^2 - v^2} \iff y^2 = \frac{c^2L^2 - v^2L^2}{c^2} \quad (6)$$

We can subtract the last equations to get

$$c^2t^2 - y^2 = c^2t'^2 - L^2 - v^2(t'^2 - L^2/c^2) = c^2t'^2 - L^2$$

In general, we can replace y and L by some distance that does not necessarily has a 0 in some coordinate and take the general formula:

$$c^2t^2 - (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) = c^2t'^2 - (x'^2 + y'^2 + z'^2)$$

Thus, this is the *egregious* Minkowski metric. This derivation is so simple and straightforward and does not involve any *fancy* mathematics or assumptions, which makes us wonder why this derivation is rarely seen on textbooks.

We can also use an orthogonal light pulse to better understand the breakdown of simultaneity because, as we discussed earlier with our Galilean model, non-simultaneity is not a direct consequence of the constant speed of light principle.

Figure 3: Simultaneous light beams at P and Q for A and transformed rays for observer B.

Suppose observer A sees two light pulses emitted orthogonally: one along the line of motion of observer B, and another perpendicular to it. These pulses are set up in such a way that the orthogonal ray reaches a point P in the ceiling and some detector Q are at the same distance for observer A. Thus, if both origins for A and B are the same $O = O'$ and the two light pulses are emitted simultaneously at the origin. Then, after some time t one reaches the ceiling and the other reaches the detector for observer A, this implies that for observer A these events happened simultaneously because such distances are the same $\overline{OP} = \overline{OQ} = x = y = ct$.

However, in B's frame, the orthogonal pulse must cover a different distance $\overline{O'P'} = ct'$, and although we don't really know if the two pulses intersect at the same point so now we must deal with the complication discussed earlier that observers should see the same object just with different measures.

It's a bit intuitive why it should be the same point with a simple geometric argument. We have that the squared triangle formed by $\overline{Q'P'} = ct$, $\overline{O'Q'} = vt'$ and the diagonal $\overline{O'P'} = ct'$ (the total path of the orthogonal pulse in B's frame) now has a hypotenuse larger than $\overline{O'Q'}$. However, we can easily verify that $\overline{O'Q'} = vt'$, that is, the projection of the diagonal ct' has the same distance as the detector at Q' and the origin of the light pulses O'.

We can add a third light pulse at the ceiling R but over the detector at Q such that the segment \overline{RQ} is orthogonal to the line of motion of B and thus, parallel to \overline{OP} . Yet, for observer B the segment $\overline{O'P'}$ is also parallel to $\overline{Q'R'}$ because both are orthogonal to A and therefore, the projection over the line of motion is 0 and are seen for observer B as something moving with speed vt' . This means that $\overline{P'R'} = \overline{O'Q'} = vt'$, that is, if we measure the distance from the origin of the light beams with a speed v it will take t' time units to reach the detector. However, if we know that $v < c$ and we also want to measure the distance from the origin to the detector with the speed of light, it cannot reach that detector the same time t' , it will instead take some time t'_1 .

But we have already stated that $vt' < ct'$ and therefore, $ct'_1 < ct'$, which implies

that the two light pulses cannot reach the ceiling and the detector simultaneously for B .

In conclusion, we derived the Minkowski metric not solely from the postulate of the constancy of the speed of light, but by also invoking the less-discussed assumption that only motion along the line of travel alters coordinates—orthogonal directions remain unaffected. But, by doing so, we realized that these postulates break down the simultaneity of observers but, at the same time, they allow observers to agree that they are seeing the very same object, even if they disagree on every coordinate.

This should have been a somewhat happy ending for us. But instead, it reads like a tragedy once you start asking questions, not only related to simultaneity, but also more mathematical like “Why is everything on a plane?” or “What principle tells us light cannot have torsion?”, you realize there’s no way back. And dear Lord, I wish I’d never asked those questions.

8.3 Farewell to Professor Dingle... and Einstein

We will address later on that discussion about non-plane curves which is somehow related to our initial objection of simultaneity break down implies a logical collapse. But before doing that, we are now entitled to give a more satisfactory answer to Dingle’s objection without using Cristoffel Symbols, Levi-Civita connections or Lie derivatives, only by using *boring* plane geometry.

Dingle’s objection, to recall it briefly, accused the theory of predicting a contradiction: two observers each claiming the other’s clock runs twice as fast. However, now that we understand how non-simultaneity emerges from the Lorentz transformations, and more importantly, that it necessarily involves orthogonal light beams (since without this, we risk falling back into a Galilean model with a constant speed of light), we can now reframe Dingle’s paradox.

The answer is surprisingly simple. Imagine a pair of orthogonal light beams associated with each observer—one for A , and one for B at some point P and P' respectively such that the height is the same for both observers which is possible given that the orthogonal direction remains unchanged.

Thus, observer A may be able to say that the orthogonal light ray reached point P at time t but observer B sees that orthogonal light pulse as a slanted ray and since, the vertical distance remains unchanged for both observers, the slanted ray takes a longer route and thus, time measurements for observer B disagree with those of observer A and can even state that light pulse takes twice as time to reach point P .

This purely geometric effect shows the symmetry clearly since we can always assume there is a orthogonal light pulse for one observer but transforms into a slanted ray for the other. It does not require tenseless propositions, nor any privi-

leged frame. The entire resolution rests on the same trigonometric considerations discussed earlier.

Yet one final question may still linger in the mind of the attentive reader. Now that we can finally let Professor Dingle rest in peace... Einstein might come back from the dead and ask: “Very clever. But what happened to time dilation and length contraction?”

To be honest... I have no idea.

Our geometric derivation, which leads naturally to the Minkowski metric, makes it clear that the phenomena we call time dilation and length contraction are still encoded somewhere within the structure. What is not clear, however, is which interpretation — if any — should be granted as the correct one.

Indeed, the asymmetry we observed — that two orthogonal light pulses emitted at the same distance do not reach their targets simultaneously in a relatively moving frame — can be described in two ways. One may say that space contracted, allowing light to arrive faster. Or one may say that time dilated, so less duration was required for light to reach the same distance. The math works out identically either way. The geometry does not choose sides.

And experimental results? Well, muon decay is often cited as confirmation of time dilation: muons created in the upper atmosphere live long enough to be detected at Earth’s surface. But this too is ambiguous. One may claim the muons’ internal clocks are ticking more slowly — or one may just as well claim that, from the muons’ point of view, the Earth’s atmosphere is contracted and thinner, allowing them to cross it before decaying. The formalism accommodates both interpretations but it cannot help us to choose one over the other.

Thus, the dilemma persists: length contraction or time dilation? Or are both equally real, or equally illusory? From the geometry alone, we cannot decide. Either way, I think we have arrived to the most beautiful paradox so far: we can explain the non-simultaneity of observers but we cannot decide if clocks slow down or rods contract.

This may not seem like big deal at first but if we remember our revised version of the Dingle’s paradox appealing to non-simultaneity as also having the unwanted outcome of a breakdown of logic, we need to pick a side in order to ask if whether logical propositions can still be valid under change of coordinates.

If we stick to the Einstein’s consideration of de-synchronized clocks then length contraction is the winner since non-simultaneity is explained by a light pulse covering less distance. However, this indeed leads to inconsistency between logical

propositions because if for observer *A* the propositions

P : Light pulse 1 is at point P.

Q : Light pulse 2 is at point Q orthogonal to P.

R : Red light R is turned on.

It could be the case that for observer *A* that the following proposition is true $P \wedge Q \rightarrow R$. Yet, observer *B*, as we have seen, may have the proposition $P \rightarrow Q \rightarrow R$, if point *P* is at his line of motion.

And how can we translate this with time dilation? Again, honestly I have no idea. My example of Mr. Tompkins in *Magic Heavens* clearly explains that motion in time is more troublesome than what many apologists of B-theory of time may admit. It isn't obvious if such result of time dilation is just about being at the same place but watching the movie at a different timestamp or maybe watching it at a different frame rate? I have no idea. I may try to give a very bad attempt at using the Putnam-Penrose interpretation, with maybe a lot of misinterpretations but this is how I would understand this situation of being at different slices of time-space.

Observer *A* sees both light pulses one orthogonal and another parallel to the line of motion of observer *B* arriving at the same time. Let's say observer *A* makes the propositions:

P : Light pulse 1 arrived at point P on Monday at 5 PM.

Q : Light pulse 2 arrived at point Q orthogonal to P on Monday at 5 PM.

R : Red light R is turned on at 6 PM on Monday.

However, we know that those events *P* and *Q* cannot happen simultaneously for observer *B*. So, he will again fall into the same situation of not agreeing with the proposition $P \wedge Q \rightarrow R$ even if observer *B* claims his "now" is Friday while *A* says "now" is Tuesday.

This is where the discussion may go in separate directions one for a philosophy of realism and the other path with empiricism. For the reader more aware of philosophical dilemmas, this bifurcation may appear odd, since it should be realism vs idealism or rationalism vs empiricism, but our final questions in last section of "Why is everything is on a plane?" and "Why can the speed of light not have torsion?" will help us notice that realism and empiricism cannot have the same approach to this matter. But first, let us recall briefly those definitions of realism and empiricism:

Generic Realism: that is if a, b, and c and so on exist, and the fact that they exist and have properties such as F-ness, G-ness, and H-ness is (apart from mundane empirical dependencies of the sort sometimes encountered in everyday life)

independent of anyone's beliefs, linguistic practices, conceptual schemes, and so on.

The Empiricism Thesis: We have no source of knowledge in a particular area, S, or for the concepts we use in S other than experience. To be clear, the Empiricism thesis does not entail that we have empirical knowledge. It entails that knowledge can only be gained, if at all, by experience.

To recall the odd match up we are stating, it's worth noticing that these theses are not necessarily contradictory since one can assume objects properties are independent of beliefs or language but still claim that our knowledge of those objects can only be gained by experience. So, what's going on here why are these these now in conflict?

Well, answer is simple, yet not so simple.

We remember that our discussion of the Minkowski metric relied on two assumptions that are not necessarily true, that a light beam is a straight line and a squared triangle follows the Pythagorean theorem. However, from differential geometry we know that such assumptions already compromise our space with a metric and curvature, because even if we live on a surface and have no idea what's our extrinsic curvature, we can still realize if we are in a curved surface or not via parallel transport.

This should give realism the high ground because we are clearly stating that space-time natural properties are those of a plane with an Euclidean metric. However, here comes again physicists with their odd definitions, like that of proper time as we discussed before. Because, as we know from differential geometry, a curve with constant speed tell us nothing about its shape, given that we can always parametrize regular curves with an arc-length parametrization. So, stating that the speed of light is constant tell us nothing about the shape of a light curve unless we make further assumptions.

But, this issue is solved by physicists by stating that the speed of light is a geodesic in its respective frame. This may seem like a clever solution but, in general, is very restrictive and can only be valid on surfaces and locally. Why is that so?

Let us assume we have two observers one moving over a straight line and the other moving on a circle, but we already know what are the surfaces that have a circle and a straight line as geodesics: a plane and a sphere. Thus, speed of light must be a geodesic in its respective frame although if we impose our change of coordinates between observers to be differentiable, invertible and valid for every point in each surface we are stating a contradiction since we are saying that there is a diffeomorphism between the plane and a sphere, which we already know is not possible.

In conclusion, saying that a light beam is a geodesic in its respective frame

is very restrictive and only works between surfaces and local coordinates, not to mention that this restrictions are completely useless for a 3D curve and a plane curve because there is no local diffeomorphism between a plane and a volume.

This is where the realism and empiricism may start to clash since the realism perspective is compromised in stating what is the real nature of space-time: Is it plane or is it curved? This can help us solve a non-symmetrical change of coordinates for space and plane curves as motion frames for observers because, if some observer does not agree that a light beam follows a straight line in his frame, that is a consequence of being in a frame that is not within the "natural" motion of space-time.

However it's worth mentioning that making claims like: "Speed of light follows a geodesic but that geodesic depends on gravitational fields". Then, a realism perspective must answer what is the "natural" gravitational field for space-time, not to mention that this claim still does not solve the change of coordinates for an observer moving in a space curve and another on a plane curve.

But the realism discussion cannot end merely by declaring what is the geometric "nature" of space-time. As we have seen, there is a breakdown of logical propositions between observers. Therefore, if one wants to preserve a natural order of events, there must be a preferred frame from which that order can be consistently defined. Otherwise, if all observational frames are equally valid and yet they disagree on the order of events, then the realist must embrace a new epistemological framework.

Meanwhile, the empiricist may simply dodge the issue of logical or geometric consistency. For him, "light is a geodesic in your frame, locally" is sufficient—as long as the observations fit. But this position becomes hollow when the very observations lead to logical contradictions across frames. Pressed further, the empiricist must either revise his trust in logic itself—accepting that logic, geometry or even topology may not be universal—or else remain a utilitarian, indifferent to the implications as long as the model delivers.

This is the actual crossroad for science that Dingle may have foreseen more than half a century ago. Although, we were able to tackle his objection but only because it was a misleading argument founded on misleading conceptions about the nature of the Lorentz transformations. Yet, it would not be surprising at all if after deriving Einstein's energy equation without using the proper interval and by obtaining the Minkowski metric by a discussion that ironically is founded partially in textbooks, or even more ironically, after giving an answer to Dingle's objection with nothing more than plane geometry, many physicists may still conclude that this manuscript is just a result of "elementary" mistakes.

So I returned once more to the Magic Goddesses, seeking guidance on how to face this fate, and they answered —again, with their beautiful and charming voice:

“Magic is in the eye of the beholder. So, tell me, which one has the right answer for life: the one that sees magic in something works despite of not knowing why, the one that sees magic in understanding how it works or perhaps... the one who dances with both the certain and the uncertain?”

A Minkowski invariance for derivatives

Let's assume we have two observers A and B moving with relative speed v between each other. Also, we assume that we have a pair of smooth curves in both frames $(x(\theta), t(\theta))$ and $(x'(\theta), t'(\theta))$, respectively. If we apply the Lorentz transformation matrix for the curve $(x'(\theta), t'(\theta))$, we obtain

$$x(\theta) = \frac{x(\theta)' + vt'(\theta)}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

$$t(\theta) = \frac{x(\theta)'v/c^2 + t'(\theta)}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

Since everything depends on the parameter θ we can take the derivative of x and t respect to this parameter and obtain

$$\frac{dx}{d\theta} = \frac{dx'/d\theta + v dt'/d\theta}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dt}{d\theta} = \frac{v/c^2 dx'/d\theta + dt'/d\theta}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} \quad (8)$$

For the sake of simplicity of notation, we will change the derivative symbol into the dot notation \dot{x} since every derivative depends on the same parameter θ . Now, we need to calculate the Minkowski metric for the derivatives

$$c^2 \left(\frac{dt}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dx}{d\theta} \right)^2 = c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \dot{x}^2$$

We can use (7) and (8) to calculate the squared derivatives

$$\left(\frac{dt}{d\theta} \right)^2 = \frac{(\dot{x}' + v\dot{t}')^2}{1 - v^2/c^2} = \frac{\dot{x}'^2 + 2v\dot{x}'\dot{t}' + v^2\dot{t}'^2}{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

$$c^2 \left(\frac{dx}{d\theta} \right)^2 = \frac{(\dot{x}'v/c^2 + \dot{t}')^2}{1 - v^2/c^2} = \frac{v^2/c^2 \dot{x}'^2 + 2v\dot{x}'\dot{t}' + c^2\dot{t}'^2}{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

Now it's just subtracting last equations to obtain

$$c^2\dot{t}^2 - \dot{x}^2 = \frac{\dot{x}^2(v^2/c^2 - 1) + \dot{t}^2(c^2 - v^2)}{1 - v^2/c^2} = \frac{(c^2\dot{t}^2 - \dot{x}^2)(1 - v^2/c^2)}{1 - v^2/c^2} = c^2\dot{t}^2 - \dot{x}^2$$

Hence, it's possible to rewrite this with Leibniz notation instead

$$c^2 \left(\frac{dt}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dx}{d\theta} \right)^2 = c^2 \left(\frac{dt'}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dx'}{d\theta} \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

Thus, we have shown that the derivatives follow the Minkowski metric when we consider that there is one parameter describing both curves. Although if we had two 3D curves instead given by $(x(\theta), y(\theta), z(\theta), t(\theta))$ and $(x'(\theta), y'(\theta), z'(\theta), t'(\theta))$, we know, from section 8, that orthogonal directions are not affected by the Lorentz transformations. Therefore, if line of motion is on the first coordinate it must be true that

$$y(\theta) = y'(\theta), \quad z(\theta) = z'(\theta)$$

But this implies that

$$\left(\frac{dy}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dy'}{d\theta} \right)^2 = 0, \quad \left(\frac{dz}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dz'}{d\theta} \right)^2 = 0$$

We just need to add two zeros to either side of (9) to obtain

$$c^2 \left(\frac{dt}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dx}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dy}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dz}{d\theta} \right)^2 = c^2 \left(\frac{dt'}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dx'}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dy'}{d\theta} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dz'}{d\theta} \right)^2$$

B A letter to Herbert Dingle

Dear professor Dingle,

I don't know if you ever imagined that more than 50 years later after your publication of your objection nobody would even dare to give an elementary answer to an "elementary mistake". Yet, it pleases me to write you down this letter in order to introduce me as that nobody.

It's very strange that my journey started the very same as yours since I was very curious about the Twin's paradox but, unlike you, I don't know why I always thought Minkowski metric was only true for nothing else but light beams and there was no way you could apply it to siblings, flies or magical apple trees. So, I ventured into special relativity as just a hobby to fill out isolation during some quarantine days hoping my doubts would be cleared up... However, all I've got was disappointment.

The first odd thing I realized while I was studying by my own, was that the Lorentz factor was not a universal time dilation factor because for a light beam, another formula arises. In that moment I thought: "How can two clocks slow down differently if you measure a light beam or something else? That does not make any sense." Albeit, unlike you, professor, I'm a nobody. I do not know a Julian Huxley or a Max Born that could help me publish or explain me what's going on. I did tried with a couple of ex-classmates yet, they told me they had no time. I do not blame those classmates for not rescheduling their agenda in order to fit some time to address my dumb questions. However, after some time, I just forgot about the matter and didn't care about it for quite a long time.

Some years passed and one day I just wanted to play with an AI (a large language model that simulates human speech) and see if could "convince" the AI that special relativity was wrong. I don't know how I did it but it worked and I didn't even used my question of different formulas for time dilation. All I know is that a fire burned within me that day, something or someone, perhaps The Magic Goddesses themselves, whispered into me that I should write down my ideas, because there was some other odd things I figured out besides that double time dilation formulas.

So, from the very first moment I wrote the first sentence of my first script, I knew I was doomed: I'm a nobody and no one would dare to listen to me, unless is for upbraid me or of make fun of me. Hence, that spark that lit the fire turned into something perverse. I was no longer a nobody filling out his lone hours. This turned me into Ahab chasing down his white whale. Certainly, if Ahab succeeded, he may had became a legend but that meant anything to him, revenge was more important than any tall tales of him. I guess I should clear out the metaphor because my motif was not revenge, my perverse objective was explaining in the most stupid way as possible why special relativity or its interpretations are as lame as the ones that will make fun of me for merely questiong something that has an obvious faulty argumentation.

At some point during the writing of the first script, because this appendix is attached to the second script, I found about you professor and I read your objection. Albeit, at that point I was still too far away to give any convincing answer to myself that could solve that objection yet, at some moment, I realized about something more obscure about that objection since, even if I solved the problem with a more convincing interpretation of the symmetric clock measures between observers; non-simultaneity is screwing up logic itself. That was like a reverse Eureka moment, something like Ahab finally having the goddamn whale on sight and, just like every man driven by madness, I chased and chased my goddamn prey until I failed miserably.

Why did I failed? I don't really know how to tell but none of what I have written

feels like good conquering evil or anything close to it. Nevertheless, even if this manuscript is not even read by All Mighty God himself. I would like to inform you, professor, that I have finally gave a convincing argument for your objection, though not for my twisted revision of it. My resolution is the following:

Imagine a pair of orthogonal light beams associated with each observer—one for A, and one for B at some point P and P' respectively such that the height is the same for both observers which is possible given that the orthogonal direction remains unchanged. Thus, observer A may be able to say that the orthogonal light ray reached point P at time t but observer B sees that orthogonal light pulse as a slanted ray and since, the vertical distance remains unchanged for both observers, the slanted ray takes a longer route and thus, time measurements for observer B disagree with those of observer A and can even state that light pulse takes twice as time to reach point P.

And that's pretty much it, explanation only needed orthogonal light beams. If could go back in time, I would feel more than honored if you could revise this solution through the only eyes I could rely on that would not dare to say that the emperor is not nude.

Thank you, Herbert, for asking.

Yours in thought, from a nobody.

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